

Search for Potent Anthelmintics. Part IX : 4-Substituted-1-Piperazinylcarbonyl Acrylic/Propionic/Nitro Benzoic Acids

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Condensation of N-alkyl or aryl piperazine with maleic, succinic and 3 or 4-nitro phthalic anhydrides in the presence of acetone or benzene yielded β -(4-alkyl or aryl-1-piperazinyl-carbonyl) acrylic/propionic acids and 2-(4-alkyl or aryl-1-piperazinylcarbonyl)-3 or 4-nitro benzoic acids respectively.

HENDERSON^{1,2} has very recently reported that 2-(1-piperazinylcarbonyl) benzoic acid was found to be an anthelmintic with long lasting effect. Aroylacrylic acids^{3,4} are known to possess marked anthelmintic activity. Further, some esters of polycarboxylic acids⁵ such as succinic, maleic and phthalic acids have also shown efficacy as nematocides. So, it was felt interesting to synthesise the title acids in order to study the effect of 4-substituted-1-piperazinylcarbonyl moiety on the anthelmintic activity of these. It was also envisaged that the presence of a NO₂ group in the phenyl nucleus might augment the activity of benzoic acid derivatives to a considerable degree.

The anthelmintic activity of these compounds will be reported later on.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The infrared spectra were determined in KBr pellets on Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer. 3 and 4-Nitro phthalic

anhydrides were prepared according to a published procedure⁶. Succinic and maleic anhydrides were obtained according to the method of Vogel⁷. N-Aryl piperazines were synthesised by following the procedure of Pollard^{8,9}. N-Methyl piperazine was prepared according to a known method^{10,11}.

4-Alkyl or aryl-1-piperazinylcarbonyl acrylic/propionic/3 or 4-nitrobenzoic acids

0.01 mole of maleic/succinic/3 or 4-nitro phthalic anhydride was dissolved in dry acetone or benzene (25 ml.) and a solution of 0.01 mole of an appropriate piperazine added gradually. Excepting few cases in which there was a immediate separation of the solid product in cold, the resulting mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4 to 6 hours under anhydrous conditions. Excess of solvent was distilled off and the resulting solid crystallised from ethanol or benzene-petroleum ether.

Analytical and physical data of the prepared compounds are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE-1. β -(4-ALKYL OR ARYL-1-PIPERAZINYLCARBONYL) ACRYLIC/PROPIONIC ACIDS.

S. No.	X	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	%N	
						Found	Calcd.
1. ^a	-CH=CH-	H	139	75	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃	15.68	15.22
2.	"	CH ₃	198	70	C ₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃	14.56	14.14
3.	"	C ₆ H ₅	82	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	10.32	10.77
4.	"	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	125	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	10.64	10.22
5.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	85	56	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	9.88	10.22
6.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	90	50	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	10.66	10.22
7. ^b	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	H	142	55	C ₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃	15.32	15.05
8.	"	CH ₃	100	50	C ₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	14.51	14.00
9.	"	C ₆ H ₅	130	50	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	10.30	10.69
10.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	95	58	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	10.50	10.14

I. R. Spectral bands (cm⁻¹)

a. 3300 (NH Str.), 1630 (tert amide C=O)

b. 1725 (C=O of COOH), 1635 (tert amide C=O), 1480 (-CH₂-).

TABLE - 2. 2-(4-ALKYL OR ARYL-1-PIPERAZINYLCARBONYL)-3 OR 4-NITROBENZOIC ACIDS.

S. No.	Y	R	m p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	%N	
						Found	Calcd.
1. ^c	3-NO ₂	H	274	65	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₅	14.68	15.05
2. ^d	"	CH ₃	262	70	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅	14.80	14.34
3.	"	C ₆ H ₅	255	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	11.36	11.83
4.	"	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	238	68	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	11.70	11.38
5.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	85	50	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	11.84	11.38
6.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	82	55	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	11.02	11.38
7.	4-NO ₂	H	195	68	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₅	15.44	15.05
8.	"	CH ₃	272	70	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅	14.78	14.34
9.	"	C ₆ H ₅	205	62	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	11.56	11.83
10.	"	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	188	58	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	11.09	11.38
11.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	90	52	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	11.11	11.38
12.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	88	50	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	11.82	11.38
13.	H	CH ₃	270	60	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅	11.67	11.29
14.	"	C ₆ H ₅	160	64	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₅	8.68	9.03
15.	"	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	155	66	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅	8.24	8.64
16.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	125	56	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅	8.98	8.64
17.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	145	60	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅	9.02	8.64

I. R. Spectral bands (cm⁻¹)

- c. 1660 (tert. amide C=O), 3450 (NH Str.), 1530 and 1350 (-NO₂), 790 (arom. ring with 3 adj. H. atoms).
 d. 1710 (arom COOH), 1635 (tert. amide C=O), 1530 and 1350 (-NO₂), 780 (arom. ring with 3 adj. H. atoms).

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